

InfiniCortex:

***concurrent supercomputing across the globe
utilising trans-continental InfiniBand
and
Galaxy of Supercomputers***

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Emerging Technologies

Supercomputing14

New Orleans, 18th November 2014

Computational
Resource Centre

InfiniCortex: concurrent supercomputing across the globe utilising trans-continental InfiniBand and Galaxy of Supercomputers

1. Project description.

We propose to merge four separately important and interesting concepts integrated for the first time together to realise InfiniCortex demonstration:

- i) High bandwidth intercontinental connectivity between Asia and the USA;
- ii) InfiniBand technology over trans-continental distances using Obsidian Strategics range extenders;
- iii) Connecting separate InfiniBand sub-nets with different net topologies to create a single computational resource: Galaxy of Supercomputers
- iv) Running workflows and applications on such a distributed computational infrastructure, especially using ADIOS I/O framework.

Our initial demo set up of InfiniCortex will comprise of computing resources residing in Singapore (cluster at A*STAR), Japan (Tsubame-KFC at Tokyo Institute of Technology), Australia (large virtual cloud server based on OpenStack and InfiniBand at National Computational Infrastructure) and in the United States (University of Tennessee) as well as on the floor of SC14 Exhibition hall, at the A*CRC booth. These computers will be connected using long-distanced InfiniBand links among these five sites (Figure 1) enabled by Obsidian Strategics' SDR Longbow E100 encrypting IB range extenders and QDR Crossbow R400 InfiniBand routers (Figure 2).

Galaxy14 Network - Supercomputing 2014

Link	Data Rate	Distance / Actual	Ping / Actual
Singapore — Tokyo, Japan	2.5Gbps	5,312 km / - km	25ms / - ms
Singapore — Canberra, Australia	- Gbps	6,216 km / - km	29ms / - ms
Singapore — New Orleans, USA	10/100 Gbps	16,367 km / - km	77ms / - ms
Knoxville TN, USA — New Orleans, USA	10 Gbps	876 km / - km	4ms / - ms

Figure 1. InfiniCortex spanning three continents of the globe.

Figure 2. The network schematics of Galaxy of Supercomputers.

We have already run preliminary tests between Singapore and Australia over a non-dedicated 1Gbps link of approximately 14,500km (73.5ms) at Layer 3; and between Singapore and Japan over a partial 10 Gbps link of 6,000km (35ms) at Layer 2

We have secured a dedicated 10Gbps link between Singapore and the West Coast US which will be available from the 10th September. We are still negotiating with the trans-Pacific carrier the possibility of having 100Gbps link to be available during the SC14. The length of the optic fibre between Singapore and New Orleans is estimated at 20,000+ km and related latency is expected to be approximately 120 milliseconds, consistent with light's time-of-flight over such a distance.

Our trans-Pacific carrier will be OpticAccess. For national connectivity we will be supported by SingAREN in Singapore, NII and NICT in Japan, AARNET in Australia and ESnet, SciNet and Internet 2 in the USA. During our preliminary testing all above parties have demonstrated full dedication and ability to deliver expected results.

We scheduled progressive testing of the link from Singapore to Seattle and then to Knoxville and New Orleans between early September and mid-November. The Crossbow R400 InfiniBand routers coupled with BGFC multiple subnet InfiniBand routing algorithms, will also be tested for the first time on such a scale and for subnet management over long-distance sub-net topologies and interconnects.

For general applications, Galaxy of Supercomputers is not expected to perform as efficiently as supercomputers residing in the single datacentre due to physical limit of latency. However, our proposed solution might be very useful for specific data- and computationally intensive workflows, where big data is generated in one location, it can be partially transformed or pre-processed on another one, before reaching target computing resource and final analysis at yet another distant location. Techniques for realizing performance close to the physically consolidated case will be explored and demonstrated, using intelligent data staging to mask transit latencies and wide area RDMA to seamlessly migrate data between continents in a secure and efficient fashion.

At the SC14 we will benchmark at least two applications to demonstrate the feasibility and lasting value of our platform. The applications incorporate ADIOS, Adaptive I/O System, for big data from Oak Ridge National Laboratory, and result from long research collaborations between ORNL, University of Tennessee, Georgia Tech and Rutgers University.

The first application is the popular LAMMPS molecular dynamics simulations for material science (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Task decomposition of LAMMPS molecular dynamics code on Galaxy of Supercomputers.

The second is the Fusion experiment for which large ECEI fast camera data from Singapore to Tennessee must be transferred (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The workflow of the Fusion application on Galaxy of Supercomputers.

Additionally, we may also demonstrate the performance of multi-scale blood platelets simulation code from Stony Brook University.

Several other applications can also be demonstrated on our platform and are expected

to perform well. We expect this platform to lead the future of supercomputer developments in architecture, algorithm, and software. More importantly, many demanding applications in science, engineering, medicine and commerce may be enabled by this platform. It is not unreasonable to suggest that we might approach Exascale computing a few years sooner than originally projected by engaging the world's top supercomputers to form a colossal Galaxy of Supercomputers. This proposal is the first to demonstrate this exciting venture.

2. Project relevance to, and potential impact on SC.

This is wide-scope technology demo involving many separate technologies: optic links of very high bandwidth, InfinBand across very large distances, InfinBand routing, supercomputer topologies forming sub-nets of diverse topologies aggregated together, and specially selected applications.

This project may push forward the frontiers of SC by demonstrating the feasibility of clustering supercomputers globally at high speeds on calculated network topologies. The potential benefits of our "Galaxy of Supercomputers" project are yet to emerge in terms of emerging technologies in architectures, algorithms, software, and applications.

3. Facility requirements.

We are already been involved with SciNet to discuss the 100Gbps backhaul from Seattle via ESNNet. ESNNet Engineers have been positive about this, and we have procured 10Gbps connection for three months Sep to Nov 2014 as well as an offer of a two-week 100Gbps TransPacific test-link for demonstration purposes at SC'14 from a transpacific carrier OpticAccess to link up Singapore's SingAREN network to Seattle. Internet2 is also positive about this project and we will engage them to secure any backup links where necessary.

We will use A*CRC booth space in which we will install one 16-node Galaxy16 mounted on a standard rack. We will need one local computer and one A/V projector to display the real-time performance of our "Galaxy" spanning three continents. We will need approximately 60A of electricity for the booth and the network connection of 100 Gbps from the SciNet Network room to our A*CRC booth.

Other booths will also be integrated into the demonstration, including that of Obsidian Strategics.

4. Staffing.

A*CRC will be sending at least six staff to be involved in network component, cluster and software, presentation and discussions and other support duties. We will have at least three staff members hosting the booth at any time.

5. Presentation.

The team is expecting and prepared to give a talk in the theatre or participate in a panel describing our project anytime, anywhere at the SC14.

NOT GRID!

Computational
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**NOT
CLOUD!**

Computational
Resource Centre

InfiniCortex

**concurrent supercomputing
across the globe
utilising trans-continental InfiniBand
and
*Galaxy of Supercomputers***

Computational
Resource Centre

Team - Singapore

Team - USA

Team - Japan

Team - Australia

Commercial Partners

Commercial Sponsors

The InfiniCortex Components

1. ACA 100

Asia Connects America 100 Gbps, by November 2014

Challenge issued by Yves Poppe at APAN 37 in Budung, Indonesia, February 2014

2. InfiniBand over trans-Pacific distance

Made possible with Obsidian Strategics Longbow range extenders

3. Galaxy of Supercomputers

Supercomputer interconnect topology work

by Y. Deng, M. Michalewicz and L. Orlowski

Obsidian Strategics Crossbow InfiniBand router

4. Application layer

from simplest file transfer: dsync+

to complex workflows: ADIOS, multi-scale models

A*CRC Datacenter I

Level 17 at Fusionopolis

A*STAR Datacenter II

Matrix Building at Biopolis

Computational
Resource Centre

A*STAR

Metro-X A*CRC team:
Stephen Wong
Tay Teck Wee
Steven Chew

Mellanox Metro-X testing since early 2013
goal: to connect HPC resources at Fusionopolis with storage
and genomics pipeline at Biopolis - Matrix building

Early tests with MetroX Mellanox switches

Point to Point

One Switch

Two Switches

Long Range (2km)

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Raising Asian Research and Education Networking to a higher dimension

The ACA-100 challenge

Asia connects America at 100gbps in November
2014 at SC14 in New Orleans

Credits: Yves Poppe, APAN 37 at Bandung, Indonesia 20th January 2014

Will APAN raise to the ACA-100 challenge ?

- **Project name:** ACA-100 Asia connects America at 100gbps
- **Event :** SC14 Super Computing 2014 in November in New Orleans
- **Objective:** Illustrate the pioneering role of the R&E community and APAN in particular in R&E networking
- **Demonstration:** feasibility of a 'real' transpacific 100gbps on a single wave between Asia and SC14 in New Orleans, in cooperation with Internet2 and other counterparts. Leave it on for one year as is the case with ANA-100.
- **The extreme challenge for 2014:** extend ACA-100 all the way to Europe via internet2 and ANA-100 or it's successor...☺

Credits: Yves Poppe, APAN 37 at Bandung, Indonesia 20th January 2014

as TERENA and Internet2 did last year at ANA-100?

- **Project name:** ANA-100 transatlantic connection at 100gbps
- **Event :** Terena conference in june 2013 in Maastricht, Netherlands
- **Objective:** Illustrate the pioneering role of the R&E community in North America and Europe in particular in R&E networking
- **Demonstration:** feasibility of a 'real' transpacific 100gbps on a single wave between Internet2 and Netherlights extende to Maastricht and CERN in Geneva in cooperation with Internet2 and other counterparts. The circuit remains operational for one year after the june demo.
- **Timeframes an outcome:** an agreement to proceed was reached in april 2013; extremely tight schedule. Successful demo at Terena 2013.

Credits: Yves Poppe, APAN 37 at Bandung, Indonesia 20th January 2014

Supercomputing 2014 New Orleans, USA, 16-20 November

Event: Emerging Technologies

Galaxy14 Network - Supercomputing 2014

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Extending InfiniBand over trans-continental distances

Partners: Obsidian Strategics and A*CRC

Computational
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Capability: Bulk, Secure Data Migration at the File System Level

- NASA helped Obsidian define market requirements for enhancing Wide Area InfiniBand connections with suitable encryption and authentication.
- Obsidian created a large-scale file system synchronization tool, dsync+, to help NASA and others simplify the transfer of huge scientific data sets across distance using Longbows – supporting non-InfiniBand storage arrays providing they are fast enough to keep up.

Unprotected ftp transfers – **30 Mbytes/second** file-level copies.

Secure dsync+/Longbow E100 transfers – **940 Mbytes/second** file-level copies.

Mission:

Scalable, stable, secure and high performance RDMA interconnects

The Obsidian team firmly believes in the technical superiority of the InfiniBand protocol, and develops proprietary technologies to move InfiniBand beyond today's typical HPC model into fabrics worthy of both Exascale HPC and Enterprise deployments, which have similar requirements.

Obsidian's Longbow and Crossbow platforms provide four main capability sets:

Range Extension

Lossless InfiniBand is incapable of significant link lengths due to buffer credit starvation. Longbows provide transparent buffer credit extension and interface between LAN and optical WANs.

Encryption and Authentication

Longbow E100 provides AES protection on the WAN segments, protecting data and also infrastructure against intrusions while X100 interoperates with military Type-1 encryptors. Critical for certain industries, including finance, health care and military/ intelligence.

Multi-Subnet Routing

Crossbow and certain Longbow devices provide hardware InfiniBand routing, which is critical for inter-organizational communication, fault isolation, overcoming LID space limits and supporting compound topologies.

Enterprise-Grade Subnet Management

Obsidian's BGFC provides n-way active SA clusters, mathematically proven dead-lock free forwarding tables, direct support for InfiniBand routers and many features intended to facilitate Exascale deployment concerning performance scaling, fault tolerance and deterministic routing engines.

High Performance System Area Networking

LOCALITY SERVICES

Remote Data Visualization - ultra high definition, fast & interactive real-time collaboration

Compute Aggregation - dynamically construct and operate geographically distributed server clusters

Global Data Migration - move large data securely across the world at local access speeds

Key Enabler - InfiniBand Over the WAN

Lossless transport:

- Cluster interconnect now a global transport protocol
- Deterministic data flows
- Distance-insensitive throughput
- Very low latency & jitter
- Seamless to applications
- RDMA support – scales with memory bandwidth, not CPU speed
- A Unified Fabric able to carry storage protocols

Patent granted: US (#7,843,962) also UK, Australia, Mexico, Japan, Russia, Canada, China, Korea and Israel (pending worldwide).

Existing Hardware Portfolio

Full-production models:

Longbow C100 – 10G IB range extender
Dark Fiber/ xWDM Metro Area Networks (80 km)

Longbow X100 (Military) – 10G IB range extender/ router
10GbE/ OC-192, Wide Area Networks (unlimited distance)

Longbow E100 – 10G IB range extender/ router/ crypto
Dark Fiber/10GbE, Wide Area Networks (unlimited distance)

A-CWDM81 – 10G Optical Mux/Demux
Nine CWDM channels, Metro Area Networks (80 km)

Longbow C400 – 40G IB range extender
Dark Fiber/ xWDM Regional Area Networks (1~1,600 km)

(All devices support secure standards-based out-of-band management over Ethernet and serial ports, including SNMP, SSH-CLI (Cisco syntax) and HTTPS interactive GUI for configuration, performance/state monitoring, logging and firmware/hardware updates)

Crossbow Device

Crossbow R400-6 – 40G

Six-port native IB router (enables multi-subnet LAN fabrics)

Longbow Devices (Future)

Longbow E1000 – 100G IB range extender

Dark Fiber/ 100GbE Wide Area Networks (Global km)

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to multi-scale models

Galaxy of Supercomputers

- Supercomputers located at different geolocations connected into a ***Nodes of Super-Network (Super-Graph)***
- Supercomputers may have arbitrary interconnect topologies
- Galaxy of Supercomputers is a topological concept and is based on a topology with small diameter and lowest possible link number
- In terms of graph representation it may be realised as ***embedding*** of graphs representing Supercomputers' topologies into a graph representing the Galaxy topology

32k5 ⊗ 32k5

Embedding of a 5-connected graph on 32 nodes into itself proves to be comparable to TOFU or 5D torus with equal or similar number of nodes.

Name of topology	Number of nodes	Number of link	Diameter	Mean path length
32k5 ⊗ 32k5	1024	2640	9	6.31
Tofu (6x5x3)	1080	5400	9	5.04
5D torus (4x4x4x4x4)	1024	5120	10	5
Tofu (4x4x8)	1536	7680	11	5.67

Galaxies of Supercomputers and their underlying interconnect topologies hierarchies

Lukasz P. Orlowski¹, Yuefan Deng^{1,2,3} and Marek T. Michalewicz¹

¹ A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore 138632, Singapore; ² Stony Brook University, New York 11794-3600, USA; ³ National Supercomputer Centre in Jinan, Shandong Province, P. R. China

poster at ISC'14, Leipzig, June 2014

Galaxy of supercomputers: proof of concept

System Software: BGFC - Next Generation InfiniBand Subnet Manager

A 1Gbyte/second 40km routed and encrypted InfiniBand link was demonstrated at SC12, using BGFC to orchestrate the fabric comprising two subnets with very different internal topologies ("compound topology").

Galaxy of supercomputers: proof of concept

Capability: Low Latency Server Aggregation

- NASA Ames purchased 16 Longbow C100 units expanding their flagship Itanium-based *Columbia* supercomputer to share jobs across one-mile of dark fiber to a second building.
- Expansion of supercomputers and data centers must contend with power and cooling constraints – these problems can often be resolved by Longbows.
- A similar model works for the linking of containerized data center pods in the field or within modular data centers.

Galaxy14 Network - Topology - Supercomputing 2014

— 4X InfiniBand LAN
— 10G WAN

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InGeneoS

Intercontinental Genetic sequencing over trans-Pacific networks and Supercomputers

- Jakub Chrzesczyk, NCI Cloud Team
- Andrew Howard, NCI HPC Team

Slides 31-43 credits: J. Chrzesczyk & A. Howard, NCI

- NCI and A*Star collaboration
- Goals
 - Utilise trans-Pacific extended InfiniBand and shared SuperComputer resources to accelerate DNA analysis
 - Transfer large (~300Gb) genetic sequence data sets generated in Canberra from NCI to A*Star Singapore for analysis on the A*Star Aurora large memory system with the results visualised in New Orleans (SC14)
 - Utilise NCI High Performance InfiniBand Cloud HPC systems for visualisation of genetic data results produced by Aurora

HPC clouds
Reference Mapping


```
TTGGGTAAAGGCTA...TTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
A...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
AT...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATG...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATGG...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATGGG...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATGGGA...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATGGGAA...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA  
ATGGGAA...GTTGATGCTAAGGTTGGAA
```


SAM
(Sequence alignment/map)

NGS reads

Singapore
Computational
Resource Centre

NGS
(Next-Generation Sequencing)

SAM files

BAM
(Binary alignment/map)

SC14
New Orleans, LA | hpc matters.

Analysis
Visualization

Emerging Supercomputing Technologies

1. INTERCONTINENTAL offsite supercomputing
2. Integrating HPC clusters and HPC clouds
3. Making distant IB networks to be local ones
4. Super fast data transportation (0.83Gb/s)
5. Solutions to migrate and analyse BIG data
6. Proof-of-concept by a Bioinformatics NGS workflow

A*Star Aurora

- OpenStack Cloud supported by a 56Gbs InfiniBand fabric
 - High Performance IB MPI
 - High Performance Lustre File System access
- Built using Mellanox Neutron modules
- Flexible top performance computational resources ‘on demand’
- Flexible OS and application stack supported by an I/O architecture which includes local Solid State Disk and high performance large file storage using Lustre

GENETIC SEQUENCE:
GATACGGAGTTTA.....A 381GB

 381G

 1143G

<i>1 second</i>	<i>900 MB</i>
<i>1 minute</i>	<i>54 GB</i>
<i>1 hour</i>	<i>3.24 TB</i>
<i>1 day</i>	<i>77 TB</i>
<i>1 week</i>	<i>539 TB</i>
<i>1 month</i>	<i>2.3 PB</i>

Network Environment for SC14 RDMA Test Tokyo Tech

Server & Network (Tokyo Tech)

A decorative vertical bar on the left side of the slide, consisting of several thin, parallel vertical lines in shades of gray. To the right of these lines are several overlapping circles of varying sizes, all in a dark blue color. The largest circle is at the top left, and smaller circles are arranged in a descending, slightly curved pattern towards the bottom right.

MIDDLEWARE AND APPLICATIONS FOR A GALAXY OF SUPERCOMPUTERS

Slides 47-56 credit: Matthew Wolf, Scott Klasky, Jong Choi, Manish Parashar, C-S. Cheng, Greg Eisenhauer, Glenn Brook, Tahsin Kurc (in arbitrary order)

Main concepts for ADIOS

- I/O Componentization for Data-at-Rest and Data-in-Motion
- Service Oriented Architecture for Extreme scaling computing
- Self Describing data movement/storage
- Main paper to cite

Q. Liu, J. Logan, Y. Tian, H. Abbasi, N. Podhorszki, J. Choi, S. Klasky, R. Tchoua, J. Lofstead, R. Oldfield, M. Parashar, N. Samatova, K. Schwan, A. Shoshani, M. Wolf, K. Wu, W. Yu, "Hello ADIOS: the challenges and lessons of developing leadership class I/O frameworks", *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 2013

Introduction to Staging

- Initial development as a research effort to minimize I/O overhead
- Draws from past work on threaded I/O
- Exploits network hardware support for fast data transfer to remote memory

Using Staging as an I/O burst buffer

Hasan Abbasi, Matthew Wolf, Greg Eisenhauer, Scott Klasky, Karsten Schwan, Fang Zheng: DataStager: scalable data staging services for petascale applications. Cluster Computing 13(3): 277-290 (2010)

Ciprian Docan, Manish Parashar, Scott Klasky: DataSpaces: an interaction and coordination framework for coupled simulation workflows. Cluster Computing 15(2): 163-181 (2012)

WAN Staging – Adios Solution

- Research on stream-based WAN data process
 - In-transit processing (supporting data-in-memory)
 - Data indexing & query to reduce network payload
 - WAN transportation: FlexPath (GATech), DataSpaces (Rutgers), ICEE (ORNL/LBNL)

Near Real Time (NRT) Application Scenario: Plasma Disruption Detection

- Plasma disruption
 - Lead to the loss of stability and/or confinement of tokamak plasmas
 - Cause fast thermal and/or current quench
 - Could damage multi-billion tokamak
- The experimental facility may not have enough computing power for the necessary data processing
- Distributed in transient processing
 - Make more processing power available
 - Allow more scientists to participate in the data analysis operations and monitor the experiment remotely
 - Enable scientists to share knowledge and processes

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Blobs in fusion reaction Blob trajectory
(Source: EPSI project)

Microscopy Image Analysis

(Stony Brook University (SBU) & Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL))

- **Significance:** Understanding of disease morphology at micro-anatomic level has tremendous potential for better diagnosis and better understanding of disease mechanisms.
- **Challenge:** Significant processing power to rapidly analyze tissue slide images (40Kx40K to 120Kx120K pixels in resolution) in order to quantitatively assess disease condition. Machines near slide repositories may not have sufficient power.
- **Approach:** Split processing workflow. (1) Partition slide image into tiles; (2) Process each tile at low-resolution to see if it contains information; (3) Send selected full-resolution tiles to a powerful cluster over wide-area network; (4) Perform analysis (nuclear segmentation and features) on full-resolution tiles on powerful cluster.
- **Technologies:** (1) SORNL ADIOS for wide-area, efficient transfers; (2) Longbow for very fast, low-latency connection; (3) SBU RT for high-throughput, pipelined processing on cluster.
- **Demo:** Tissue slides on machine in Singapore. Analysis done on cluster at Georgia Tech. Segmentation results displayed on client machine.

Snapshot of adaptive processing of a remote slide (53Kx36K pixel resolution).

Work supported in part by NCI and NLM: 1U24CA180924, R01LM011119-01, R01LM009239 grants, and ORNL SDAV and JFA.

Molecular Dynamics – Design of Materials

- This demonstration is based off a scenario from materials scientists interested in understanding fracture in nano-structured materials
- It uses LAMMPS to simulate the block of nano-structured metal while under stress.
- Simulation proceeds until the first plastic deformation (start of fracture) is detected.
- At that first fracture, the system is fully characterized to understand where and, hopefully, why things broke.

Coupling codes with ADIOS+staging method

ADIOS + DataSpaces/DIMES/FLEXPATH

- + asynchronous communication
- + easy, commonly-used APIs
- + fast and scalable data movement
- + not affected by parallel IO performance
- data aggregation/transformation at the coupler

Fusion code coupling (CPES project)

Interactive visualization pipeline of fusion simulation, analysis code and parallel viz. tool

Wide-Area Dataspaces

Wide-area globally shared DataSpace abstraction achieved by interconnecting multiple DataSpaces instances

- Asynchronous (TCP/IP-based) control network enables $O(1)$ data lookup across DataSpaces instances
- Asynchronous (RDMA and GridFTP based) provide efficient data transfers

Data **put** to a DataSpaces instance is distributed based on

1. Demand -- application requests to **get** or prefetch the data
2. Availability -- pending **get** request - data becomes available once it is **put** by another application
3. Locality -- data is copied to the DataSpaces that is local to the application making the **get** request

FLEXPATH: TYPE-BASED PUBLISH/ SUBSCRIBE FOR COLLABORATIVE SCIENCE

- Type: data + metadata
- Subscriptions: data type and slices/derivations
 - MxN data distributions & transformations
- Direct connect vs. traditional brokered pub/sub

Direct-Connect Pub/Sub

The Singaporean Team

A*CRC

Dr Marek Michalewicz (PI)

A/Prof Tan Tin Wee (PI)

Prof Yuefan Deng (PI, Galaxy of Supercomputers)

Yves Poppe (International Carriers)

Tan Geok Lian (Networking)

Lim Seng (Networking)

Dr Jonathan Low (H/W, S/W, Applications)

Dr Dominic Chien (S/W, Applications)

Dr Liou Sing-Wu (S/W, Applications)

Paul Hiew (H/W)

Stephen Wong (iVEC connection)

SingAREN

A/Prof Francis Lee

Prof Lawrence Wong

NTU

Stanley Goh

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Oak Ridge National Lab

Dr Scott Klasky

Dr Jong Choi

Rutgers University

Prof Manish Parashar

Georgia Tech

Prof Matthew Wolf

Prof Greg Eisenhauer

Stony Brook University

Prof Deng Yuefan

Prof Tahsin Kurc

University of Tennessee

Glenn Brook

The Australian Team

Canberra: National Computing Infrastructure

NCI Directorate

Prof. Lindsay Botten

Allan Williams

NCI HPC Systems & Cloud Services

Dr. Muhammad Atif

Andrew Wellington

Dongyang Li

Jakub Chruszczyk

NCI Storage & Infrastructure

Daniel Rodwell

Others at NCI (Network)

Jason Andrade

Darren Coleman

ARRNET

Bruce Morgan

Computational
Resource Centre

The Japanese Team

TiTech: Tsubame-KFC: Prof Satoshi Matsuoka, S. Muira *et al.*

TEIN-JP NOC Team, KDDI

SINET Team, NII

NICT

Computational
Resource Centre

Obsidian Strategics

Dr. David Southwell

Jason Gunthorpe

Please visit our demonstrations at booth #2520 A*CRC #548 Obsidian Strategics

